

Framework for operational Digital Twins of Urban Drainage Systems

Miloš MILAŠINOVIĆ¹, Luka VINOKIĆ², Željko VASILIĆ³, Milan GOCIĆ⁴, Veljko PRODANOVIĆ⁵

^{1,3} Digital Water Engineering Lab, University of Belgrade, Faculty of Civil Engineering, Serbia

email: mmilasinovic@grf.bg.ac.rs (for author 1)

email: zvasilic@grf.bg.ac.rs (for author 3)

^{2,5} The Institute for Artificial Intelligence Research and Development of Serbia

email: luka.vinokic@ivi.ac.rs (for author 2)

email: veljko.prodanovic@ivi.ac.rs (for author 5)

⁴ University of Nis – Faculty of Civil Engineering and Architecture, Serbia

email: milan.gocic@gaf.ni.ac.rs (for author 4)

ABSTRACT

Operating Urban Drainage Systems (UDSs) is becoming increasingly challenging due to growing complexity and performance demands. These challenges can be effectively addressed through digitalization and innovative decision-support solutions, such as Digital Twins (DTs). However, establishing and operating a DT involves numerous technical and organizational difficulties. To enable wider adoption of this technology in the urban water sector, the development of integrated and interoperable tools is essential. This paper presents a Data–Information–Knowledge–Wisdom (DIKW) pipeline designed to support the operation of DTs for asset management in UDSs. The approach is demonstrated through a Belgrade case study, highlighting the benefits of connecting diverse tools, such as machine learning and physically based models within a unified framework.

1. Introduction

Urban Drainage Systems (UDSs) face increasing challenges such as ageing infrastructure, climate change, and a shortage of qualified personnel, requiring fast and innovative solutions. The ongoing digitalization across industries offers opportunities to develop tools that enhance UDS operation under such demanding conditions. Digital Twins (DTs) have emerged as powerful technologies for representing physical systems, improving resource efficiency, and providing safe virtual environments for testing extreme scenarios and supporting operational decisions. For UDSs, where system complexity and daily operational demands are high, DTs should: (i) provide real-time insights into system performance - detecting inflows, infiltration, exfiltration (seepage), blockages, and other inefficiencies, and (ii) enable virtual risk assessments to guide maintenance and investment priorities. Developing such DTs requires an integrated framework combining: (i) a Geographic Information System (GIS) database, (ii) sensor networks, (iii) sensor data management systems, (iv) simulation models, and (v) algorithms linking data and models. Each component presents challenges, including geometry gaps in GIS data (Hajibabei et al. 2025), sensor anomalies and failures (Kim & Bartos 2025), and the need for data assimilation to connect sensor data and models (Bartos & Kerkez 2021). This research introduces a novel framework that transforms raw sensor data into actionable insights to support asset management in UDSs.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Overview

The framework for developing operational DTs for UDSs as asset management support builds upon the Data–Information–Knowledge–Wisdom (DIKW) pipeline (Figure 1). This DIKW-based architecture systematically transforms raw data into actionable intelligence for UDS management. In operation, DT periodically or on demand collects raw sensor data, analyses them using an ensemble of machine learning (ML) models, and assimilates the processed data into a SWMM (Storm Water Management Model) simulation model. This continuous data assimilation keeps the DT synchronized with observed system behavior, ensuring a live and reliable foundation for informed decision-making.

Fig. 1. DIKW pipeline for operational Digital Twin of Urban Drainage Systems

Sensor Data Management System (SDMS) addresses common challenges in sensor network data collection by detecting and removing anomalies (e.g., outliers, drifts, noise bursts) and recovering missing data caused by sensor faults or anomaly removal. An ensemble of machine learning models (LSTM, CNN, TCN) has been developed and trained for each sensor to ensure robust data processing and quality assurance.

Data assimilation (DA) connects the processed sensor data and simulation model to reflect reality. In this manner, model provides an accurate near-time representation of the physical system and even allows for the detection of abnormal processes (e.g., inflow).

2.2. Case study

Described framework was tested for the part of Belgrade UDS (Fig. 2.a). For demonstration purposes, 12 nodes were selected as sensor nodes, and a synthetic dataset was created from a long-term SWMM simulation. Scenario with 3 faulty sensors (no data records for the entire period) was analyzed to demonstrate the potential of the proposed approach in data recovery and improving the system state representation by data assimilation.

Fig. 2. a) case study, b) head hydrographs at validation location

3. Results and discussion

Baseline simulation with unreliable input data and DA (only with data from active sensors) underestimates the system state (NSE = 0.70 at head validation node). Using sensor data management system to reconstruct head time series at the locations of faulty sensors and coupling it with DA improves the quality of system state estimation (NSE = 0.93), showing the value of the entire DIKW approach under the DTs.

4. Conclusions

The study presents Digital Twin Framework for UDSs, emphasizing the coupling of ML techniques and physically-based model of the system through DIKW pipeline for better system insights in near real-time.

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